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Multi-actor Network to Boost Short Food Supply Chains Across Europe

**EU4Advice and COREnet
launch the “Local Food
Advisors’ Journey 2026”**

JOIN OUR
NETWORK

the European Advisory Network for SFSCs (EAN-SFSC) and to actively involve advisors in shaping it.

The Advisors' Journey offers a flexible and evolving package of activities for advisors who are part of the COREnet and EU4Advice shared network. The Advisors' Journey, built as a "work in progress", encourages continuous feedback, ideas and proposals from SFSC advisors to improve this exchange. Activities will include webinars, trainings, practice abstracts and short project videos, helping advisors discover innovative approaches and learn from each other.

Advisinars & Resources

The Advisors 2026 Journey will provide a rich array of webinars, trainings, practice abstracts and short project videos, which will provide numerous opportunities to study innovative approaches to the advisory practice, share their experience, and learn with colleagues all over Europe.

Central to the programme is the **Advisinars** which is a monthly online webinar of 1hr that happens on the 3rd Monday of the month at 10:00 CET, which is a regular space where advisors in all the participating countries can converse and get inspired (and ask questions). The trip started on 19 January.

[Learn more](#)

Women in SFSC

An interview with...

EU4Advice

Nita van Dam

Sabine van Giesbergen

This International Women's Day, we honoured the women who are changing the way Europe eats. 🌱

There are women producers, farmers and food entrepreneurs behind the scenes at Short Food Supply Chains (SFSC) who do much more than just grow and sell.

Read the interviews:

- [Nita van Dam](#)
- [Sabine van Giesbergen](#)

Producers' Interviews

Watch the Interviews!

EU4Advice

Iván Guimerá

Bruno Muñoz

Julio Quilis

interview some producers of La Huerta de Valencia and get to know the challenges and necessities they had and how a project like EU4Advice and a network of advisors could help producers like them to overcome the risks and problems. Watch the interviews with:

- [Iván Guimerá](#)
- [Bruno Muñoz](#)
- [Julio Quilis](#)

EU4Advice: Building Tomorrow's Advisory Leaders Across Europe

training curriculum at the **International System Dynamics and Innovation in Food Networks Conference**, where a diverse audience of international and local experts was invited to review and discuss the proposed learning framework.

[Read the article](#)

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